

INFLUENCE OF CONCENTRATION ON THE PROPERTIES OF ARABIC ACID SOLUTION

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Arabic acid solution is a polydisperse system consisting of micelles of different states of aggregation. The trend of the changes of the properties with concentration studied here indicates that there is probably a formation of aggregates in this system too, but such phenomenon does not appear to begin abruptly at any particular concentration. Rather it is more probable that the process of aggregation is progressive, right from very low concentrations. Although there appear breaks in the curves showing variation of different properties as functions of concentration, these do not all occur at the same concentration.

Gum arabic occurs in nature as an exudate of *Acacia arabica* (Beng., Babla). As isolated by usual methods it consists mostly of the salt of a complex acid with potassium, calcium and magnesium (cf. O'Sullivan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1884, 45, 41) as inferred from the nature of the ash obtained by incinerating the purified gum. By hydrolysing the gum with sulphuric acid O' Sullivan obtained a pentose sugar (arabinose), a relatively small quantity of hexose (galactose) and an acid which he termed "arabic acid." More recent work shows that this acid consists of a compound of *d*-glycuronic acid and galactose containing other carbohydrate molecules (*d*-galactose, *l*-arabinose and rhamnose) attached to it by glycosidic binding (Butler and Cretcher, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1519; Norman, *Biochem. J.*, 1929, 23, 24, 524; Weinmann, *Ber.*, 1929, 62, 1637). This acid kernel has been known as the galactose-glycuronic acid (more generally as aldobionic acid) the constitution and composition of which have been investigated in a comparatively recent work by Hotchkins and Goebel (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 858).

Properties of this acid in aqueous solution present some peculiar features which were looked upon by the earlier workers as difficult of explanation and attributed to the colloidal nature of the solution. Thomas and Murray (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 676) carried out systematic investigations on its electrochemical and osmotic properties in solution. More recently Pauli and Ripper (*Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 62, 162) as well as Pauli and Palmrich (*ibid.*, 1937, 79, 63), Taft and Malm (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 874), and Briggs (*ibid.*, 1934, 38, 867) have made important contributions to our knowledge of the electrochemical properties of the acid hydrosol prepared and purified by electro dialysis. Kruyt and Tendeloo (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1929, 29, 396) from viscosity measurements in presence and absence of electrolytes have concluded that the aqueous solution of the gum acid has the characteristics of a lyophilic colloid. Pauli and Ripper (*loc. cit.*) have suggested that the ionogenic part of the complex glycuronic acid, viz., the carboxyl group, imparts a negative charge to the sol particles by its electrolytic dissociation, whereas the attached carbohydrate groups principally behave as the neutral part whose hydration imparts lyophilic character to the sol.

The arabic acid in aqueous solution has thus been looked upon as a colloidal electrolyte. Physical properties, specially electrochemical properties of the hydrosols of colloidal electrolytes show characteristic variations with concentration as has been shown by McBain and co-workers (McBain and Betz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1909), Lottermoser and Puschel (*Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 63, 175) and Hartley and co-workers (vide the summarising paper, *Kolloid Z.*, 1939, 88, 22). A study of the nature of these variations

has undoubtedly served to elucidate the state of aggregation of the particles existing in such sols and also to understand the anomalous electrochemical and osmotic properties of a number of such substances. The present work aims at an investigation into the influence of concentration on different properties of the aqueous solution along this line and at a correct assessment of the role of the colloid character of the solution upon its behaviour.

EXPERIMENTAL

Acid sols used in the present investigation were prepared by purification and hydrolysis of the gum in the following manner.

Gum arabic (Merck Alniss. p_H VII; 30 g.) was dissolved in 250 c. c. of equilibrium water (1.2×10^{-3} mho at 35°) and filtered; 30 g. of NaCl of reagent quality were added to it and dissolved by shaking; the resulting sodium salt was then precipitated out by addition of 700 c. c. of rectified spirit and separated by filtration. The residue was then pressed between filter papers, dissolved again in 150 c. c. water and 17 g. of NaCl were added to it. The sodium salt was once again precipitated by excess of alcohol. This process of solution and precipitation of the Na salt was repeated several times in order to remove completely the basic radicals, e.g., K, Ca and Mg. Three such repetitions were found sufficient for the purpose (cf. Bungenberg de Jong and Teunissen, *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1938, **47**, 254).

The sodium salt was next dissolved in 100 c. c. of water mixed with about 50 c. c. 3*N*-HCl and the salt precipitated again by 500 c. c. of rectified spirit, filtered, the residue washed with 75% alcohol till free from chlorine, and then with alcohol-water mixture (50:50) several times. The residue was then dried at room temperature (30°) on a clock glass.

The purified acid, thus obtained, was preserved in the solid state in a well cleaned resistance glass bottle from which 1% sol was prepared by weighing out the requisite amount in equilibrium water and shaking it thoroughly in a mechanical shaker for half an hour. The resulting sol was preserved in similar bottles, sterilised by continued steaming, under a layer of toluene. The p_H and specific conductance were found to remain constant in presence of toluene. After four weeks a slight turbidity appeared, but no other change was indicated.

After six weeks, however, the p_H and specific conductance of the sol indicated definite signs of change (p_H changed from 2.95 to 2.71 and sp. conductance from 4.50×10^{-4} to 4.75×10^{-4} mho). The sols used in the present investigation were in no case four weeks old and different samples were prepared. The purified solid appeared to suffer a loss of peptisability with time and each time the starting sol was made from freshly prepared gum acid. Consequently it was ascertained by experiments that the sols were comparable with each other so far as the properties studied in the present investigation were concerned provided they had the same acid contents (cf. Taft and Malm, *loc. cit.*).

The acid used for preparation of the sol was tested before for nitrogen, phosphorus, sulphur and chlorine and also for reducing sugars. Specific rotation was -27° and the ash content, 0.12%. These properties compare very favourably with those of previous workers.

The effect of concentration was mainly studied with respect to (i) ultrafiltration, (ii) specific conductance, (iii) free and total acidity, (iv) dissociation constant and (v) cataphoretic velocity.

Hydrogen-ion activity and total acidity were determined electrochemically by titration with NaOH with a hydrogen electrode. The platinum deposit of the electrode was removed and replatinisation done every day after measurements to avoid erratic behaviours of the electrode (vide Mukherjee *et al.*, *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1936, 6, 517).

To ascertain whether equilibrium between the gum acid and the base has been attained in potentiometric and conductometric titrations within the usual time allowed in such experiments, the same volume of the sol (10 c. c.) as used in these experiments was taken in a series of Jena bottles, mixed with corresponding amounts of the base and kept for 24 hours after which the specific conductance and p^H of these samples were determined. The results obtained indicated that the equilibrium in the interaction of the acid with NaOH was reached within a short time (cf. Briggs, *loc. cit.*). Cataphoretic velocity (C. V.) was measured in the same manner as reported in a previous paper by the author (cf. Mukherjee and Sarkar, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 65).

DISCUSSION

Ultrafiltration.—The sol was observed not to pass through a parchment nor a celloidion membrane during dialysis but it could be ultrafiltered through celloid membrane No. 600, under pressure. The process was, however, extremely slow. The ultrafiltrate presented an appearance similar to that of the parent sol; its specific conductance was high being of the same order as that of the sol from which it was derived. The total acidity as determined by titration with NaOH was also high being about 50% of the parent sol. Whether the acid in the ultrafiltrate was present in true solution could not, however, be ascertained *a priori*. Ultramicroscopic examination revealed the presence of a large number of particles executing brisk Brownian movement. Their number was observed to be smaller than that in the parent sol as determined by a preliminary counting.

TABLE I

Arabic acid solution.

Temp. = 35°

Conc. (g./litre)	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$ mho.	Sp. cond. of ultrafiltrate $\times 10^4$ mho.	Conc. (g./litre)	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$ mho.	Sp. cond. of ultrafiltrate $\times 10^4$ mho.
1.12	0.75	0.67	2.25	1.75	0.92
1.40	0.90	0.75	3.60	2.30	1.50
1.80	1.30	0.80	9.40	2.87	1.72

Sols of different concentrations were ultrafiltered and in every case a difference in the specific conductance between the sol and its ultrafiltrate was observed to exist. Although the difference became gradually smaller with decreasing concentration, it persisted even up to the lowest concentration observed by us (vide Table I).

These observations, however, bring out that arabic acid sol is a polydisperse system which contains particles of different size. Further corroboration is obtained from the observation that the sol also contains particles of microscopic size which are visible by an ordinary microscope with magnification of about $\times 600$.

Specific and Equivalent Conductance.—The relevant data have been presented in Table II.

TABLE II

*Arabic acid solution.*Temp. = $35^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. Sp. cond. of water used = 1.1×10^{-6} mho at 35° .

Conc. in g./l.(c)	\sqrt{c} .	Sp. cond. (κ) obs. $\times 10^{-6}$ mho.	α_H calc. from ρ_H	Sp. cond. calc. from $\alpha_H \times 10^{-6}$ mho.	Equiv. cond. (Λ) per g./litre.
0.25	0.50	0.186	0.32	0.138	7.44×10^{-3}
0.40	0.63	0.288	0.65	0.260	7.20
0.90	0.95	0.594	1.48	0.592	6.60
1.50	1.30	0.730	2.00	0.800	4.20
4.00	2.00	1.800	6.60	2.640	4.50
7.00	2.70	3.240	10.50	4.200	4.60
8.00	2.80	3.540	11.10	4.500	4.50

Since the variations in specific conductance do not show any point of particular interest and hence these have not been graphically shown. Instead, the equivalent conductance derived from these have been shown in Fig. 1 against square root of concentration. Since these acids (as will be shown in a future communication) have no fixed total acidity which has been observed to show variations with the nature of the bases used for inter action, it is difficult to estimate the equivalent weight of arabic acid, and so the equivalent conductance cannot be calculated as in ordinary acids. In this case therefore a quantity (Λ) has been defined as the conductance offered by a solution sufficient in volume to contain 1 g. of the acid and placed between two electrodes of indefinite size (cf. Mukherjee and Sarkar, *loc. cit.*).

Fig. 1

Fig. 2.

This will be strictly proportional to the equivalent conductance. The $\Lambda-\sqrt{c}$ curve, according to Onsager's equation

$$\Lambda c = \Lambda^{\circ} - k\sqrt{c}$$

(where Λ° stands for the equivalent conductance at infinite dilution and k is a constant) should be a straight line sloping downwards with increase in \sqrt{c} . The graph as shown in Fig. 1 is, however, not a straight line but a curve sloping downwards with a kink at a concentration of about 0.8 g. of the acid per litre. The curve, however, reaches almost a constant value at higher concentration and does not show any minimum.

The kink observed in the $\Lambda-\sqrt{c}$ curves at low concentrations has been looked upon as indications of aggregate formation in solutions of colloidal electrolytes like soap solutions and solutions of the salts of different long chain fatty acids and long chain sulphonic acids (cf. McBain, *loc. cit.* Lottermoser and co-workers, *loc. cit.* Hartley, *loc. cit.*). A similar line of argument would also suggest the existence of aggregate formation in this case as well. This aspect will be judged in the light of evidences obtained from behaviour of other properties in the following sections.

It will not be irrelevant to raise one pertinent question in this connection as to whether the Onsager's equation can be applied to the present system. The Debye-Hückel interionic attraction theory, of which Onsager's equation forms only an extension, assumes complete dissociation of the electrolyte which is far from true in the present system, as evident from its low specific conductance. The assumption of spherical symmetry, which is another important point on which the calculations are based, cannot be justified in the present case, since here even the simple anions are much larger and mostly consist of sugar molecules with an ionisable carboxyl group situated at one end. The distribution of counter ions (H-ions) is far from uniform or symmetrical round each anion. And although it can be visualised that hydrogen ions are distributed round each anion, it is difficult to visualise how micellar anions will be distributed round each hydrogen-ion which is an important assumption in the interionic attraction theory. Moreover, the hydration of the carbohydrate part makes the picture more complex.

It will so be observed that the values of specific conductance are low indicating a low degree of dissociation of the acid. Another interesting feature is that the observed values of specific conductance are much lower than those obtained by calculation from the hydrogen-ion activity alone of the solution as determined from its p_H (vide column 5 of Table II) at higher concentrations but become almost equal in dilute solutions. Thus in the arabic acid solution there exists a discrepancy between the hydrogen-ion activity and specific conductance. It is, however, difficult to visualise how hydrogen ions, which register their potential (*i.e.*, are active), fail to contribute to specific conductance. This is also against the accepted views in electrochemistry. Probably the assumption of independent migration of ions, on which these calculations are based, is responsible for such anomalies. If, however, a lower value of ionic conductance be assumed for H-ions due to interionic attractions, the corrections introduced are expected to remove the discrepancy to a certain extent.

Free and Total Acidity.—The free acidity (a_H) or the hydrogen-ion activity has been calculated from the p_H values determined potentiometrically. The total acidity (c)

has been worked out from the potentiometric titration of the acid with NaOH. The data appear in Table III.

TABLE III

Arabic acid solution.

Temp. = $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Conc. (g./l.)	pH.	Free acidity $a_H \times 10^4 N.$	Total acidity $c_H \times 10^4 N.$	a_H/c_H ratio (=f).	Total acidity $\times 10^4 N$ (conductometric)
0.33	4.26	0.55	2.80	0.197	—
0.44	4.16	0.70	3.80	0.184	3.72
0.55	4.05	0.89	4.80	0.185	4.83
0.66	3.99	1.02	5.60	0.182	5.58
0.77	3.91	1.23	7.00	0.186	6.96
0.88	3.83	1.48	7.60	0.190	7.55
0.99	3.79	1.60	8.60	0.186	—
1.10	3.78	1.66	9.50	0.179	—
1.21	3.75	1.76	10.5	0.167	—
1.32	3.72	1.92	11.4	0.168	11.29
1.43	3.70	1.96	12.3	0.160	12.29
1.65	3.68	2.10	14.3	0.149	14.10
1.89	3.68	2.08	17.1	0.121	16.95
2.20	3.38	2.21	19.0	0.115	18.90

The variations of a_H with concentration (c) have been presented in Fig. 2. The curve shows a progressive increase with concentration and runs smooth. A close scrutiny of the total acidities (c_H) from column 4 of Table III will show that they vary linearly with concentration, which signifies that the total acidity per g. of the acid does not change with concentration.

Thus the absence of any break in these curves does not help very much in supplying any evidence with regard to the formation of aggregates in the system. The ratio of free to total acidity ($a/c_H=f$) (shown in column 5, Table III) was therefore drawn against concentration with a view to bringing in further analysis of these data. The curve, shown in Fig. 3, evidently passes through a small minimum followed by a maximum at low concentrations. The sharp decrease beyond the maximum occurs at a concentration of about 0.9 g./litre and it decreases steadily at higher concentrations.

Fig. 4

Fig. 3

The potentiometric titration curves with NaOH from which the total acidities were determined as shown in Fig. 4, present the characteristic features of a strong acid at higher concentrations. With increasing dilution the initial flat portion of the curve tends to be smaller and smaller, thus simulating the features of weak acids to a certain extent. The p_H of neutralisation, however, varies very little with concentration and occurs in close vicinity of p_H 7, which is again a characteristic feature of strong acids.*

Conductometric titration curves (Fig. 5), however, show two inflexion points. At first the specific conductance diminishes rapidly with the addition of the alkali, and beyond the first inflexion it tends to increase to a certain extent till the second inflexion is reached, after which the curve has a steeper and linear rise corresponding to the alkali line. The first inflexion point in the conductometric titration curve approximately corresponds to the neutralisation of free acidity (hydrogen-ion activity) as obtained from p_H measurements.

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

The second inflexion point followed by the alkali line probably indicates the neutralisation of the total acid. Compared with potentiometric titration data (column 6, Table III) values of total acidity obtained for corresponding concentrations by the conductometric method show fair agreement. Equivalent weight of the acid, as calculated from the base required for complete neutralisation, comes out to be 1184 approximately which shows a satisfactory agreement with the value of 1175 obtained by Thomas and Murray (*loc. cit.*) and 1210 observed by Bungenberg de Jong (*loc. cit.*). The base required for neutralisation of 1 g. of the acid has been calculated to be 84.4×10^{-5} equivalents of NaOH.

The Dissociation Constant.—The dissociation constant of the acid cannot obviously be calculated from the potentiometric titration curves, as they resemble those of strong acids and Henderson's equation for calculation of pK cannot be applied. From conductometric titrations the dissociation constant can be calculated if we remember that the first inflexion point of such curves gives the free acidity which, may roughly be taken to be the hydrogen-ion concentration and that the concentration of the anions is equal to the hydrogen-ion activity or free acidity of the solution. With these assumptions the dissociation constant,

$$K = \frac{(C^{\text{H}})^2}{C_{\text{H}} - C^{\text{H}}} \text{ where } C \text{ stands for the hydrogen-ion concentration at the first } C_{\text{H}} - C^{\text{H}} \text{ inflexion.}$$

The values of K obtained in this way are given in Table IV.

Table IV.

Conc. of acid (g./litre).	Dissociation constant $\times 10^5$.	Conc. of acid (g./litre).	Dissociation const $\times 10^5$.
0.11	0.398	1.40	3.0*
0.22	0.79	1.80	3.7*
0.73	1.80	2.25	13.1
0.90	2.5*	3.60	17.7
1.12	2.5*	9.4	29.6

The dissociation constants have an order of 10^{-5} which indicates a weak character of the acid, while the potentiometric titration curves resemble those of strong acids. Again, the dissociation constant exhibits variation with concentration for which reason it is more or less a misnomer to call it a constant. The nature of the variations has been shown in Fig. 6. The curve shows a slow increase at lower concentrations followed by a region of constant value (0.90 to 1.80 g./litre marked by asterisks in Table IV). Beyond this region the curve shoots up, followed again by a region of slow but steady rise. The experiment was repeated in a second specimen, the curve for which runs almost parallel to the previous one.

The diminution of the slope of the curve at higher concentrations is suggestive of a tendency to reach a constant value at still higher concentrations. Pauli and Palmrich (*loc. cit.*), however, observed a steady increase of the dissociation constant with a tendency

to reach a constant value at higher concentrations. Their observations, however, did not extend to low concentrations, and hence they missed the peculiar nature of the variation of this property.

Two different view points have, however, been advanced by Pauli and co-workers (*loc. cit.*). Valko (*Kolloid Z*, 1930, **51**, 130) has suggested that the dissociation constant, which is a ratio of the two velocity constants (*viz.*, those of the forward and backward reactions of the reversible dissociation process), must be influenced by a change in one or both the velocity constants. In a binary dissociation process, if it be assumed that one of the products of dissociation be congealed or removed due to association to form bigger micelles, the rate of the reverse reaction will be considerably diminished due to diminished chances of collision. This will tend to increase the value of K . In the light of these observations the increase of K should be due to aggregate formation proceeding in this case, and since this increase of K goes on right from very low concentrations, it may be inferred that aggregation also proceeds in this system from low concentrations as well.

The second view point was proposed by Briggs (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, **38**, 867) who regards the acid as a polybasic one the dissociation of which in aqueous solution does not proceed in a simple and uniform manner like that of a monobasic acid at all concentrations. At higher concentrations the primary dissociation becomes prominent, at lower concentrations the secondary, tertiary and other types of dissociation may appear which are generally of weak character. He cites the nature of the potentiometric titration curves in support of his views, but this does not appear to be plausible as these curves resemble those of strong monobasic acids, rather than a polybasic acid having dissociation constants separated from one another by a narrow margin. Assuming the theory of widely separated charges as proposed by Simms (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 1239, 1251) the monobasic nature of the potentiometric titration curves can be understood as the result of aggregation or association, in which case also the successive stages of the dissociation of the acid cannot be looked upon as being the same as the dissociation of a polybasic acid in successive stages.

Hence, the plausible conclusions from the variation of K with concentration are that probably some type of aggregation proceeds within the system as proposed by Valko (*loc. cit.*). As to the shape and nature of the potentiometric titration curves the discussion is postponed until further work is done on the interaction of this acid with bases.

Cataphoretic Velocity (C. V.).—Results of cataphoretic measurements in the case of arabic acid in the same way as referred to in a previous paper by one of the authors (*vide Mukherjee and Sarkar, loc. cit.*) have been presented in Table V and graphically shown in Fig. 7.

TABLE V

Conc. (g/litre).	C.V. $\times 10^4$.	Conc. (g/litre).	C.V. $\times 10^4$.
0.125	1.2	1.50	4.2
0.25	2.0	2.00	2.9
0.50	2.9	4.00	2.2
0.75	4.0	8.00	1.25
1.00	5.0	10.0	1.60

The curve evidently exhibits a maximum at a concentration of 1.0 g./litre, which is quite close to the concentration where $\Lambda-\sqrt{c}$ and a_H/c_H-c curves exhibit their breaks (about 0.9 g./litre in Figs. 1 and 3). The increase in C. V. indicates an increase in con-

Fig. 7

ductance on the part of the micelle anion. Hartley (*loc. cit.*) reports a rise of equivalent conductance of the micelle ions in his system, and McBain (*loc. cit.*) reports a rise of transport number above unity in Na-soap solutions. Both of them have explained their observations as due to the formation of aggregates on the part of the paraffin chain ions to form micelles. In the present system, since an increase in C.V. is observed from very low concentrations (even below that indicated as the critical concentration from the $\Lambda-\sqrt{c}$ curves) a progressive aggregate formation right from low concentrations appears to be suggestive. The cause of a decrease of cataphoretic velocity is not, however, properly understood. More work seems to be essential for a definite conclusion on this point.

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